

Decomposition behavior of platinum clusters supported on ceria and γ -alumina in presence of carbon monoxide

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Abstract. Since the catalytic behavior of supported platinum species strongly depends on their nuclearity under the reaction conditions, in this study we addressed the stability of platinum species in presence of CO. We applied density functional modeling to clarify the effect of the CO coverage on the structure and stability of small platinum clusters deposited on $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ and $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3(001)$ surfaces and on a ceria nanoparticle. The stability was evaluated with respect to decomposition of the clusters to Pt, $\text{Pt}^0(\text{CO})$ and/or $\text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$ species. The results suggest that decomposition of pristine platinum clusters to Pt^0 atoms is endothermic on all considered supports. On the other hand, the formation of $\text{Pt}^0(\text{CO})$ monocarbonyls is essentially energy neutral when the platinum cluster deposited on ceria nanoparticle or ceria (111) surface is fully covered by CO molecules. Formation of $\text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$ species can occur only when the support is small ceria nanoparticle which ensures low-coordinated O centers and easily reducible Ce^{4+} ions. On $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3(001)$ surface the platinum cluster remains stable with respect to decomposition even when it is fully covered by CO but the interaction of the cluster with alumina surface is strongly weakened. Thus, based on the results one may suppose that under CO pressure platinum clusters behaves differently depending on the support – decomposition to neutral monocarbonyls on ceria surface and to cationic complexes on ceria nanoparticle, while on alumina the carbonylated cluster remains intact but almost detached from the surface.

Introduction

An ongoing debate in catalytic community is connected with the type of the catalytically active species in systems containing supported noble metals.^{1,2} On the one hand, the reaction may occur on metal particles or clusters, while on the other hand the catalytic sites may be isolated mononuclear species as metal ions. The nuclearity and oxidation state of the supported metal species depend on the chemical nature of the metal and the support as well as

on the preparation and treatment of the catalytic system.^{3,4} They also may vary before, during and after the catalytic process due to interaction with reactant/product molecules.⁵ In the present study we focused on the latter problem studying the influence of adsorbed CO (as reactant) on the structure and decomposition of small platinum clusters deposited on ceria or alumina. Systems containing supported platinum show high catalytic activity and are widely used as catalysts for CO oxidation under various conditions,⁶⁻⁹ water gas shift reaction,¹⁰⁻¹⁴ and many other reactions as often are supported on ceria or γ -alumina.^{15,16} Although, it is well-known that the role of platinum is crucial in many reactions especially for the oxidation of CO, the oxidation state of the active Pt species is still insufficiently elucidated.

In a detailed study Fu et al.¹ investigated catalytic efficiency of Pt/CeO₂ system for water-gas shift reaction and reported that the active sites for the reaction may not be the noble nanoparticles (NPs), but most likely a small positively charged metal species strongly bound to the ceria surface. Bruix et al.¹⁷ also found that Pt-CeO₂ nanomaterials containing surface Pt²⁺ species show good catalytic properties for anode in fuel-cells. Such species, located in square-planar position on {100} facets, remain stable with respect to the processes of reduction, sintering or bulk diffusion even at high temperatures. However, on all other adsorption sites on the ceria nanoparticles the Pt remains in oxidation state zero and is not stable with respect to sintering to larger Pt clusters and particles.^{17,18}

Since during the process of CO conversion the platinum moieties of the Pt-based catalysts are expected to be covered by CO molecules, we modeled the influence of the presence of CO to the processes of sintering/agglomeration. In particular, we modeled a transfer of single Pt atom as well as of Pt(CO) or Pt²⁺(CO)₂ species from small platinum clusters to the surface of the support. To highlight the differences between behavior of platinum on reducible and on non-reducible support we considered ceria and alumina. The unique properties of ceria originate from the ability of cerium cation to change reversibly its oxidation state.¹⁹ A reduction can occur, when an oxygen vacancy is created (two Ce⁴⁺ cations are reduced to Ce³⁺ per each vacancy)^{20,21} or by deposition of noble metal clusters.^{22,23} Since the reducibility of the ceria-based systems was found to increase when the support is nanostructured,²⁴ we also studied the decomposition of platinum cluster on ceria nanoparticle. For ceria we modeled Pt clusters supported on the most stable (111) surface,²⁵ while on γ -Al₂O₃ we have selected (001) surface,^{26,27} which we have used in our previous study.²⁸ In order to investigate the influence of the support morphology, the calculations were done also with platinum species supported on Ce₂₁O₄₂ nanoparticle.

Computational details and models

We performed density functional periodic plane wave calculations, using the Vienna *ab initio* simulation package (VASP)^{29,30} with the gradient corrected PW91 exchange-correlation functional³¹ For the ceria systems is used DFT+U approach as the U parameter was set to 4.0 eV, as in previous studies.^{23,24,32,33} The valence wave functions were expanded to a plane wave basis with energy cut-off of 415 eV using pseudopotentials to describe the electron-ion interactions within the projector augmented waves (PAW) approach.³⁴ Γ -point calculations are performed.

The CeO₂(111) surface is modelled with a slab Ce₃₂O₆₄ of two CeO₂ (six atomic) layers and cell parameters: $a = 13.224 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 17.634 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 19.353 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = \beta = 90^\circ$, $\gamma = 60^\circ$. The vacuum space between slabs is 15 \AA . The model of ceria nanoparticle Ce₂₁O₄₂ has a diameter of about 1 nm.^{24,33} A cubic $20 \times 20 \times 20 \text{ \AA}$ unit cell is used in order to prevent the interactions between the nanoparticles from the neighboring cells.

For the calculations with γ -Al₂O₃ we employed a crystallographic structure of bulk γ -Al₂O₃, according to M. Digne et al.,³⁵ which we used in our recent study.²⁸ The space group is P21/m; a (\AA) 5.587, b (\AA) 8.413, c (\AA) 8.068, β ($^\circ$) 90.59. The slab of γ -Al₂O₃ contains 96 Al₂O₃ units (480 atoms). The vacuum gap between slabs is 15 \AA .

For all structures on CeO₂(111) surface, we performed spin-polarized calculations with a different number of unpaired electrons and we found that for most of the systems the spin state with two unpaired electrons is the most stable. However, the closed-shell singlet solution is more favorable for the models with CO molecules adsorbed on Pt_n clusters supported on ceria nanoparticle and for all models with γ -Al₂O₃.

Results and discussion

The structures with the supported Pt clusters (with or without CO ligands) are denoted as: *a*, *b*, *c*, *d*, *e*, *f*, *g*, *h* and *i*. The type of the transferred Pt(CO)_X, (X=0-2) species is added in the notation of the modeled structures.

I. Pt₁₀(CO)_m/CeO₂(111) systems

The Pt₁₀ cluster model deposited on ceria (111) surface (Figure 1, str. *a*) consists of two well-defined layers with arrangement similar to the bulk metal. The top layer consists of three Pt centers thus forming the smallest possible {111} facet, while the bottom one, which is in contact with ceria support consists of seven Pt atoms forming seven Pt-O contacts. In this system nine of the Pt centers are accessible for CO adsorption and only one is inside the cluster. The deposition of the platinum cluster induces spontaneous reduction of the ceria surface as one Ce⁴⁺ cation is reduced to Ce³⁺, which is in agreement with previous studies of a Pt₈/CeO₂ system.^{23,32,36} We also modeled a structure with a transfer of a single platinum atom from the pristine Pt₁₀ cluster to ceria surface (Fig. 1, str. *a-Pt* and Table 1). Such process is calculated to be strongly endothermic by 204 kJ/mol. In both structures *a* and *a-Pt* only one Ce⁴⁺ cation is reduced, but its location on the surface is different. In structure *a-Pt*, the Ce³⁺ cation is bound with one of the surface O, which is coordinated to the transferred Pt atom, while in structure *a*, the Ce³⁺ cation is bound with surface O coordinated with one of the Pt atoms from the cluster.

Next, we adsorbed linearly two CO molecules on top Pt atoms from the Pt₁₀ cluster, structure *b*, where the number of Pt-O contacts is seven. From this structure we checked again the possibilities for a transfer of a Pt atom to the ceria support. When a single Pt atom is transferred the obtained structure str. *b-Pt* is by 182 kJ/mol less stable than the initial str. *b*. It is interesting that in this case two Ce⁴⁺ cations are reduced, which means that there is a transfer of one more electron from the platinum cluster to the ceria support. Another possibility is to transfer a platinum dicarbonyl complex to the support, as shown in Figure 1, str. *b-Pt(CO)₂*. This structure contains deposited bare Pt₉ cluster and co-adsorbed Pt(CO)₂ complex. The Pt(CO)₂ unit is bound to two O centers from ceria surface, thus forming a symmetric square-planar complex, which implies 2+ oxidation state of Pt.³⁷ The length of both Pt²⁺-C bond is 189 pm. The elongation of the C-O bonds in the two adsorbed CO ligands with respect to the isolated CO molecule is less than 1 pm. The oxidation of the transferred Pt atom to Pt²⁺ cation results in reduction of two additional Ce⁴⁺ ions. Hence, there are three Ce³⁺ cations in the obtained system – two are bound with the O centers coordinated with the platinum cation and the third one is close to the Pt cluster. This model is by 318 kJ/mol less stable than the initial structure with two CO molecules linearly adsorbed on Pt atoms from the Pt₁₀ cluster (str. *b*) implying that such transfer of Pt²⁺(CO)₂ in this case is strongly unfavorable.

In order to investigate the influence of CO concentration on the process of Pt segregation, we also considered a model with one ligand per each surface Pt atom – nine CO molecules in

total (see Fig. 1, str. *c*). In the optimized structure, eight of the CO molecules are coordinated linearly and the other one is in a bridge position. There is one Ce^{3+} cation in the structure, similar to the structure with bare Pt_{10} cluster. The number Pt-O contacts is reduced to four and the Ce^{3+} cation is connected to three of O centers close to platinum atoms. Similarly to structures *a-Pt* and *b-Pt*, we considered first a transfer of a single platinum atom from the structure *c*, forming *c-Pt*. The obtained model is by 215 kJ/mol less stable than structure *c* and contains two Ce^{3+} cations, one of which is bound to the O center coordinated to the transferred Pt and the other one is close to the Pt_9 cluster.

From structure *c*, we modeled two structures with $\text{Pt}_9(\text{CO})_7$ cluster and a co-adsorbed $\text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$ unit bound to two surface O centers as in str. *b-Pt(CO)₂* (Fig. 1, str. *c-Pt(CO)₂-1* and *c-Pt(CO)₂-2*). In the two models Pt center is taken from the bottom and top layer of platinum atoms in the structures *c-Pt(CO)₂-1* and *c-Pt(CO)₂-2*, respectively. However, in the optimized *c-Pt(CO)₂-2* structure the top {111} facet is recovered, since one of the Pt atoms from the bottom layer moved to the top layer. The *c-Pt(CO)₂-1* and *c-Pt(CO)₂-2* structures are less stable by 47 kJ/mol and 92 kJ/mol, respectively, than the initial structure *c*. Although in both cases the process of $\text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$ transfer is not favorable, the subtraction of $\text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$ species is significantly less endothermic compared with those for transfer of a single Pt atom from a cluster without CO adsorbate, 204 kJ/mol, and of a $\text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$ species when only two CO molecules are adsorbed on the platinum cluster, 318 kJ/mol.

Due to the formation of Pt^{2+} cation in these structures the number of Ce^{3+} cations is increased to three (*c-Pt(CO)₂-2*) and four (*c-Pt(CO)₂-1*). Two of the Ce^{3+} cations are close to the $\text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$ species similar to the situation in structure *b-Pt(CO)₂*. For both structures, the elongation of the C-O bonds in the two CO molecules bound to Pt^{2+} cation is similar to corresponding elongation in str. *b-Pt(CO)₂* and is about 0.8 pm. In the $\text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$ complex, the Pt-C and Pt-O distances are 189 pm and about 201 pm, respectively. As a comparison in the initial structure *c*, the elongation of C-O bond lengths for the linearly adsorbed CO ligands is in the range 1.8 – 2.7 pm, the Pt-C and Pt-O bond lengths are 184 – 185 and 205 – 206 pm, respectively.

From str. *c-Pt(CO)₂-1*, we obtained a monocarbonyl complex, str. *c-Pt(CO)*, in which one of the CO molecules is returned back to the platinum cluster. This model is less stable by only 3 kJ/mol with respect to the initial str. *c* and in it Pt is in oxidation state zero. The Pt atom is bound only to one surface O center at a distance of 199 pm. The Pt – C bond, 183 pm, is shorter with 6 pm than in the $\text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$ complexes. The structure contains only two Ce^{3+} , which are located near the metal cluster.

We also considered a structure, where ten CO molecules were adsorbed on the Pt cluster. In this case, eight of the CO molecules are adsorbed at top positions, one at threefold and one at bridge position (str. *d*). Two Ce^{3+} cations are formed and they are bound to O centers coordinated to Pt atoms from the cluster. We considered a transfer of $\text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$ complex to the ceria support (structure *d-Pt(CO)₂*), similar to the case of *c-Pt(CO)₂-I* structure. The transfer is again endothermic by 49 kJ/mol. The oxidation of the platinum center to 2+ in the $\text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$ complex causes a reduction of only one additional Ce^{4+} cation, while the second electron is located on the platinum cluster. The elongation of C-O bonds in the two adsorbed ligands, as well as the Pt-C and Pt-O distances are essentially identical as the corresponding distances in the other modeled structures with a formation of $\text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$ species.

A transfer of a single $\text{Pt}^0(\text{CO})$ unit from structure *d* (see str. *d-Pt(CO)*) is unfavorable by only 8 kJ/mol. As in the str. *c-Pt(CO)*, the Pt atom is bound only to one surface O center at a distance of 199 pm.

In order to analyze the effect of the CO adsorption on the interaction of the platinum cluster with ceria surface we consider the shortest Pt-O contacts with bond distance smaller than 230 pm, which correspond to the first O-shell.³⁸ For $\text{Pt}_{10}/\text{CeO}_2$ structure before adsorption of CO, str. *a* (see Table 1) the shortest Pt-O bond lengths vary in the region 199-214 pm and the average values are about 205 pm as the number of the contacts is 7. After adsorption of two CO molecules (str. *b*), the corresponding average value and the number of the Pt-O contacts remain similar to the modeled structure *a* as the distances vary from 202 pm to 213 pm. When the platinum cluster is covered by 9 or 10 CO (str. *c* and *d*), the number of short Pt-O contacts below the threshold of 230 pm decreases to only 4 and 5, respectively, and the average Pt-O distance increases to 213 pm. Thus, increased CO coverage of the platinum cluster reduces the binding of the cluster to the support.

II. $\text{Pt}_8(\text{CO})_m/\text{Ce}_{21}\text{O}_{42}$ systems

In order to study the influence of the size of the ceria support we also considered a model with Pt_8 cluster supported on a small $\text{Ce}_{21}\text{O}_{42}$ nanoparticle.^{32,36,37} We considered the most stable $\text{Pt}_8/\text{Ce}_{21}\text{O}_{42}$ structure found in the study of Vayssilov et al.³⁶, which is shown here as str. *e* in Fig.2. A transfer of a single platinum center modeled in structure *e-Pt-I* is strongly exothermic process by 189 kJ/mol in line with previous theoretical results.^{17,18} In this case Pt is located at the small {100} facet forming square-planar complex with four O centers. Hence, the oxidation state of the co-adsorbed Pt is 2+ and two additional Ce^{3+} cations are formed. As shown previously¹⁸ adsorption of mononuclear Pt species on the other surface positions of

Ce₂₁O₄₂ nanoparticle leads to formation of neutral Pt species bound to two surface O centers from the {100} facet (str. *e-Pt-2*) or from the particle edge. The transfer of the Pt atom in this case is endothermic with respect to str. *e* by 86 kJ/mol.

In order to investigate the influence of the CO coverage on the stability of the platinum cluster we modeled structures with seven and twelve CO molecules. In str. *f* seven CO molecules are adsorbed linearly on the metal cluster, except one CO ligand, which is coordinated in a bridge position. The transfer of Pt²⁺(CO)₂ complex from structure *f* (Fig. 2, see str. *f-Pt(CO)₂*) on the surface of the nanoparticle is still slightly endothermic, by 17 kJ/mol (Table 2), which is much lower than the process on CeO₂(111) surface.

The adsorption of additional five CO molecules to the Pt₈(CO)₇ complex changes significantly the relative stability of the models. The initial structure with twelve CO on the Pt₈ cluster is shown on Fig. 2, str. *g*. Five CO molecules are in bridge positions as two are bound to bottom Pt atoms, two – to top Pt atoms and the last one is bound to one top and one bottom Pt atoms. The other ligands are linearly adsorbed. The transfer of the Pt²⁺(CO)₂ complex from this structure is calculated exothermic by -75 and -18 kJ/mol for structures *g-Pt(CO)₂-1* and *g-Pt(CO)₂-2*, respectively. In the two structures the Pt²⁺(CO)₂ complex is bound to two low-coordinated O centers from different part of the ceria nanoparticle - at the small (100) facet of the nanoparticle and at the corner between two (111) facets (see str. *g-Pt(CO)₂-1* and *g-Pt(CO)₂-2*). Thus, the stability of the complex depends strongly on their location on the nanoparticle. As expected, both structures have four Ce³⁺ ions.

We also modeled a transfer of Pt⁰(CO) unit from structures *f* and *g*. Similar to the situation on CeO₂(111) surface, here again the co-adsorbed Pt is in oxidation state zero in both structures. The transfer from the Pt₈(CO)₇ cluster is endothermic by 22 kJ/mol (str. *g-Pt(CO)*), however when five additional CO molecules are adsorbed the process becomes exothermic by -35 kJ/mol (str. *g-Pt(CO)*).

The Pt-C bond lengths in the co-adsorbed Pt²⁺(CO)₂ species in the structures *f-Pt(CO)₂*, *g-Pt(CO)₂-1*, and *g-Pt(CO)₂-2* do not differ from the same distances in the corresponding structures for the ceria (111) surface model. The elongation of C-O bonds in the two adsorbed CO molecules bound to Pt²⁺ is slightly larger by 0.1-0.3 pm in comparison to the corresponding lengths on the CeO₂(111) models. In the Pt(CO) units, where the oxidation state of Pt is 0, the C-O bond length in the coordinated ligand is significantly elongated by 2.5 – 2.6 pm with respect to the isolated CO molecule in gas phase. For the ceria slab structures, this elongation is 2.2 - 2.3 pm. As expected,³⁹ the negative correlation between the lengths of C-O and Pt-C bonds is also observed in the different models with transferred Pt(CO)_x species.

Comparing the geometries of $\text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$ and $\text{Pt}^0(\text{CO})$ complexes, we found that in the structures with $\text{Pt}(\text{CO})$ units the Pt-C bond length is shorter, 183 and 182 pm in the slab and NP models, respectively, and the elongation of the C-O bond, ~2.5 pm, is larger compared to the corresponding values in the $\text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$ complexes, 189 and ~1 pm, respectively for the Pt-C and C-O bond lengths.

The Pt-O distances in the transferred complexes $\text{Pt}^0(\text{CO})$ and $\text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$ on ceria surface and ceria nanoparticle are in the same range, 199-203 pm. In structure *e-Pt-1*, where the single platinum species are in four-fold coordination as Pt^{2+} , the four Pt-O distances are identical, 205 pm, which is in line with our previous results.¹⁸ In the case of co-adsorbed single Pt^0 atom (str. *e-Pt-2*) the transferred platinum atom is bound to two O centers at distances of 199 and 207 pm.

Similar to the situation on ceria surface, here we also analyze the interaction of the platinum cluster with ceria support and the same effect of the CO molecules is observed. In the structure with pristine Pt_8 cluster the number of the Pt-O contacts is five with average value of 205 pm, while upon adsorption of seven and twelve CO molecules the number of contacts decreases to three and the average distance increases to 207 and 224 pm, respectively.

III. $\text{Pt}_{10}(\text{CO})_m/\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3(001)$ systems

Since $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ is often used as catalyst support we also modeled structures with pristine Pt_{10} cluster deposited on (001) surface of this material (see structure *h*, Fig. 3). After the geometry optimization the structure of the platinum cluster changed strongly and differs from that of the Pt_{10} cluster on ceria (111) surface, where two easily recognizable layers are observed. The transfer of a single Pt atom from the cluster to the alumina surface is endothermic by 70 kJ/mol as the Pt atom is co-adsorbed to two oxygen centers from the alumina surface. Structure *i* represents nine CO molecules adsorbed on Pt_{10} cluster deposited on $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3(001)$ surface. Since alumina is a non-reducible oxide, the formation of $\text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$ unit on the surface is not expected. The attempt for transfer of a $\text{Pt}(\text{CO})_2$ unit from the carbonylated platinum cluster to alumina surface leads to desorption of the neutral dicarbonyl complex (see str. *i-Pt(CO)_2*). Such processes of metal-carbonyl leaching were reported earlier, for instance Chang and co-authors⁴⁰ investigated leaching of $\text{Pd}(\text{CO})_x$ ($x = 2, 3$) species from pristine or covered by CO molecules Pd(111) surface. They demonstrated that the leaching is facilitated by the low-coordinated sites and the high concentration of CO and is favorable for many of

the examined models. In our model (str. *i-Pt(CO)₂*), however, the desorption process is strongly endothermic by 178 kJ/mol.

We also modeled a transfer of a monocarbonyl Pt(CO) complex on the alumina surface. The monocarbonyl complex is bound to one of the three-coordinated surface O centers (see Fig. 3, str. *i-Pt(CO)*). Such structure with Pt₉(CO)₈ cluster and a co-adsorbed Pt(CO) species on the alumina surface is endothermic by almost 57 kJ/mol with respect to the structure with nine CO molecules adsorbed on the deposited Pt₁₀ cluster (str. *i*).

The elongation of C-O bond in the monocarbonyl complex supported on Al₂O₃(001) surface is similar to the corresponding structure on the ceria surface, 2.3 pm. The Pt-C distance, 181 pm, is very similar to those when Pt(CO) is adsorbed on the ceria surface and NP. The Pt-O bond length between the Pt(CO) species and the support, 206 pm is slightly longer than in the corresponding distances in the complexes on ceria supports. In the model with a co-adsorbed platinum atom, the distance between Pt and surface O in the transferred unit is 199 pm.

In the structures with pristine Pt₁₀ cluster, the Pt-O contacts are three with average value of 219 pm. When the Pt cluster is covered by CO ligands, the number of Pt-O contacts is reduced to only one Pt-O contact with a distance of 209 pm. The next closest Pt-O contact is as far as 247 pm. The main reason for this effect is the coordination of CO molecules to the peripheral platinum atoms at the bottom layer of the cluster, which results in saturation of those atoms and weakening of their interactions with both oxygen centers from the support and other platinum atoms of the metal cluster. Thus, the main effect of CO adsorption on the platinum cluster, supported on gamma alumina, is not decomposition of the cluster but considerable weakening of the interaction of the carbonylated metal cluster with the surface of the support. In this way the CO adsorption may facilitate the mobility of the cluster on the surface and eventually aggregation with other clusters.

IV. Reaction energies

For Pt_n(CO)_m (n = 8, 10; m = 0 – 12) complexes deposited on the different supports we have also calculated the energy for dissociation of the metal cluster to a single Pt(CO)_X (X = 0 – 2) species when Pt cluster and mononuclear species are not co-adsorbed on one surface, but located at a separate model of the corresponding support. The results of the considered model reactions are summarized in Table 4.

The decomposition of platinum cluster to isolated Pt atoms on the investigated surfaces of CeO₂(111) and γ -Al₂O₃(001) is endothermic by 94 and 47 kJ/mol, respectively. The

endothermicity of the process on $\text{Ce}_{21}\text{O}_{42}$ nanoparticle is 59 kJ/mol, while decomposition to Pt^{2+} species located at the small (100) facet of the nanoparticle¹⁷ is strongly exothermic, -137 kJ/mol. When CO is introduced in the system the decomposition of the $\text{Pt}_{10}(\text{CO})_{10}$ cluster supported in $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ surface to ten $\text{Pt}(\text{CO})$ complexes is endothermic by only 2 kJ/mol. Since the $\text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$ complexes are not stable on $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ surface, the decomposition reactions including such species are strongly endothermic by more than 100 kJ/mol. The decomposition of $\text{Pt}_{10}(\text{CO})_9$ cluster to nine $\text{Pt}(\text{CO})$ complexes and one Pt atom on $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(001)$ surface is also less endothermic, 39 kJ/mol, compared to the decomposition of pristine Pt_{10} cluster into platinum atoms. The isolated Pt atom is coordinated between two oxygen centers from the alumina surface, while the $\text{Pt}(\text{CO})$ is coordinated to only one oxygen center as also shown in structures *h-Pt* and *i-Pt(CO)* in Fig. 3.

The decomposition of $\text{Pt}_8(\text{CO})_m$ ($m = 7$ and 12) cluster on ceria nanoparticle is also significantly more exothermic than the decomposition of the pristine Pt_8 cluster to Pt atoms. The decomposition of $\text{Pt}_8(\text{CO})_7$ cluster to a single Pt atom and seven $\text{Pt}(\text{CO})$ complexes is endothermic by only 6 kJ/mol due to higher stability of $\text{Pt}(\text{CO})$ compared to Pt atoms on ceria surface. If additional five CO molecules are added and $\text{Pt}_8(\text{CO})_{12}$ cluster is formed, its decomposition to four $\text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$ and four $\text{Pt}^0(\text{CO})$ complexes becomes exothermic by -33 kJ/mol. The dissociation of the same particle to six $\text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$ and two Pt^{2+} species in square-planar coordination is even more exothermic by -51 kJ/mol owing to the high stability of the latter position of the platinum species.

Clearly, decomposition reactions of platinum carbonyl clusters are significantly more exothermic on the nanoparticle model than on the $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ surface model, since the stability of the mononuclear $\text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$ complexes is significantly higher on ceria nanoparticles than on ceria surface, due to the presence of low (two) coordinated O centers in the ceria nanoparticles which can interact strongly with the mononuclear Pt species.

Note that the decomposition behavior of carbonylated platinum clusters may differ for other surfaces of ceria or gamma alumina due to different surface structure.

Conclusions

A transfer of a single Pt, $\text{Pt}(\text{CO})$, and $\text{Pt}(\text{CO})_2$ species from deposited $\text{Pt}_n(\text{CO})_m$ ($n = 8, 10$; $m = 0 - 12$) clusters on $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ and $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3(001)$ surfaces, as well as on $\text{Ce}_{21}\text{O}_{42}$ nanoparticle is modeled. Complete decomposition of the carbonylated cluster into mononuclear species is also considered. The calculations reveal different effects of

CO coverage on the decomposition of the cluster on the three modeled types of the support:

- i) On CeO₂(111) surface decomposition of the carbonylated platinum cluster to monocarbonyl species is essentially energy neutral, which suggests that in presence of CO (e.g. under reaction conditions) the carbonylated clusters exists simultaneously with supported Pt⁰(CO) complex. Pt²⁺(CO)₂ species are much less stable. So, the active catalytic sites may be either carbonylated cluster or platinum monocarbonyls. Upon evacuation, after completion of the reaction, the isolated platinum species aggregate back into clusters since the process is strongly exothermic, by about 100 kJ/mol.
- ii) On ceria nanoparticle there is clear preference for decomposition of the carbonylated cluster to Pt²⁺(CO)₂ due to higher reducibility of the nanoparticle compared to ceria surface and the presence of low-coordinated oxygen centers. This result suggests that under reaction conditions the active species on nanostructured ceria will likely be cationic dicarbonyl species. Note that Pt²⁺(CO)₂ are more stable not only with respect to platinum cluster but also with respect to Pt²⁺ mononuclear species in the square planar coordination at {100} facet.³⁷ After the reaction the isolated platinum species will agglomerate or will move to the stable Pt²⁺ position, if appropriate {100} sites are available on the support.
- iii) On a non-reducible oxide as gamma-alumina the formation of Pt²⁺(CO)₂ species is not possible since the oxidation of Pt⁰ to Pt²⁺ cannot occur. The decompositions of the carbonylated platinum cluster to neutral Pt⁰(CO) or Pt⁰(CO)₂ complexes is calculated endothermic 39-57 kJ/mol depending on the models. Thus, in presence of CO the carbonylated cluster on γ -Al₂O₃(001) surface remains stable with respect to decomposition. On the other hand, the platinum cluster fully covered by CO is bound weaker to the alumina surface compared to bare metal cluster, as can be concluded from the decreased number of Pt-O contacts. This suggests that the CO adsorption causes detachment of the platinum cluster from the surface, which facilities its mobility.

These results may help in clarification of the type of actual catalytic species depending on the type of the support and elucidation of the dynamic changes of the nuclearity and oxidation state of platinum with variations of the conditions – treatment, reaction, or

measurement. In particular, they suggest that the types of the platinum species during the catalytic process may be different from that before or after the reaction.

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Fig. 1 Optimized structures of $Pt_n(CO)_m$ ($n = 9$ or 10 , $m = 0 - 10$) clusters and transferred $Pt(CO)_x$ ($x = 0 - 2$) complexes deposited on $CeO_2(111)$: *a* – pristine Pt_{10} cluster (top and side view); *a-Pt* – transfer of a single Pt atom from the cluster. Structures with two CO molecules: *b* – two CO molecules on top Pt atoms from the Pt_{10} cluster; *b-Pt* – $Pt_9(CO)_2$ cluster and a transferred single Pt atom; *b-Pt(CO)₂* – Pt_9 cluster and transferred $Pt^{2+}(CO)_2$ species. Structures with nine CO molecules: *c* – nine CO molecules adsorbed on Pt_{10} ; *c-Pt(CO)₂-1* and *c-Pt(CO)₂-2* – seven CO molecules adsorbed on Pt_9 and a co-adsorbed $Pt^{2+}(CO)_2$ moiety; *c-Pt(CO)* – eight CO molecules adsorbed on Pt_9 and a $Pt(CO)$ complex is transferred on ceria support; *c-Pt* – nine CO molecules adsorbed on Pt_9/CeO_2 and a single Pt atom is transferred on ceria support. Structures with ten CO molecules: *d* – $Pt_{10}(CO)_{10}$; *d-Pt(CO)₂* – $Pt_9(CO)_8$ and co-adsorbed $Pt^{2+}(CO)_2$ species; *d-Pt(CO)* – $Pt_9(CO)_9$ and co-adsorbed $Pt^0(CO)$ species. Color coding: Pt – blue, Ce^{4+} – yellow, Ce^{3+} – cyan, O – red, C – gray. Cut-off for the Ce–O, Pt–O and Pt–Pt bonds is 290, 230 and 310 pm, respectively.

Fig. 2 Optimized structures of $Pt_n(CO)_m$ ($n = 7$ or 8 , $m = 0 - 12$) clusters as well as transferred $Pt(CO)_X$ ($X = 0 - 2$) species supported on $Ce_{12}O_{24}$ NP: *e* – pristine Pt_8 ; *e-Pt-1* – Pt_7 cluster and co-adsorbed single Pt^{2+} cation; *e-Pt-2* – Pt_7 cluster and co-adsorbed single Pt^0 atom; *f* – seven CO molecules adsorbed on Pt_8 cluster; *f-Pt(CO)₂* – five CO molecules adsorbed on Pt_7 and co-adsorbed $Pt^{2+}(CO)_2$ species; *f-Pt(CO)* – six CO molecules adsorbed on Pt_7 and co-adsorbed $Pt^0(CO)$ complex; *g* – twelve CO molecules adsorbed on Pt_8 cluster; *g-Pt(CO)₂₋₁* and *g-Pt(CO)₂₋₂* – ten CO on Pt_7 and co-adsorbed $Pt^{2+}(CO)_2$ complex; *g-Pt(CO)* – eleven CO on Pt_7 and co-adsorbed $Pt^0(CO)$ complex. Structure *g-Pt(CO)₂₋₂* is rotated by 90 degrees with respect to the other structures for better visibility. Cut-off for the Ce–O, Pt–O and Pt–Pt bonds is 290, 230 and 310 pm, respectively.

Fig. 3 Optimized structures of $Pt_n(CO)_m$ ($n = 9$ or 10 , $m = 0 - 9$) clusters and transferred $Pt(CO)_x$ ($x = 0 - 2$) complexes on $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3(001)$ support: *h* – pristine Pt_{10} cluster (top and side view); *h-Pt* – transfer of single Pt atom from the cluster; *i* – $Pt_{10}(CO)_9$ cluster; *i-Pt(CO)₂* – transfer of $Pt(CO)_2$ species from the cluster; *i-Pt(CO)* – transfer of $Pt(CO)$ unit from the cluster. For visual clarity, half of the alumina of the support is not shown. Cut-off for the Al–O, Pt–O and Pt–Pt bonds is 200, 230 and 310 pm, respectively.

Table 1. Relative energies (ΔE , kJ/mol) for the transfer of $\text{Pt}(\text{CO})_X$ ($X = 0 - 2$) species from $\text{Pt}_{10}(\text{CO})_m$ ($m = 0 - 10$) clusters on $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ support with respect to the initial structures *a*, *b*, *c*, and *d*. Selected distances in the $\text{Pt}(\text{CO})_X$ species (in pm); number of Ce^{3+} cations, N; number of unpaired electrons (Ns) for the systems are also shown.

Structure	Short Description	ΔE	$\Delta d(\text{C-O})^a$	$d(\text{Pt-C})$	$d(\text{Pt-O})$	N	Ns
$\text{Pt}_{10}/\text{CeO}_2(111)$							
<i>a</i>	Pt_{10}	0			$\langle 205 \rangle / 7^b$	1	2
<i>a-Pt</i>	$\text{Pt}_9 + \text{Pt}^0$	204			203;214	1	2
$\text{Pt}_{10}(\text{CO})_2/\text{CeO}_2(111)$							
<i>b</i>	$\text{Pt}_{10}(\text{CO})_2$	0			$\langle 206 \rangle / 7^b$	0	0
<i>b-Pt</i>	$\text{Pt}_9(\text{CO})_2 + \text{Pt}^0$	182			198;202	2	2
<i>b-Pt(CO)₂</i>	$\text{Pt}_9 + \text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$	318	0.7;0.9	189;189	201;202	3	2
$\text{Pt}_{10}(\text{CO})_9/\text{CeO}_2(111)$							
<i>c</i>	$\text{Pt}_{10}(\text{CO})_9$	0			$\langle 213 \rangle / 4^b$	1	2
<i>c-Pt</i>	$\text{Pt}_9(\text{CO})_9 + \text{Pt}^0$	215			200;208	2	2
<i>c-Pt(CO)₂-1</i>	$\text{Pt}_9(\text{CO})_7 + \text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$	47	0.7;0.9	189;189	200;201	4	2
<i>c-Pt(CO)₂-2</i>	$\text{Pt}_9(\text{CO})_7 + \text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$	92	0.7;0.9	189;189	201;203	3	2
<i>c-Pt(CO)</i>	$\text{Pt}_9(\text{CO})_8 + \text{Pt}^0(\text{CO})$	3	2.2	183	199	2	2
$\text{Pt}_{10}(\text{CO})_{10}/\text{CeO}_2(111)$							
<i>d</i>	$\text{Pt}_{10}(\text{CO})_{10}$	0			$\langle 213 \rangle / 5^b$	2	2
<i>d-Pt(CO)₂</i>	$\text{Pt}_9(\text{CO})_8 + \text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$	49	0.7;0.9	189;189	201;202	3	2
<i>d-Pt(CO)</i>	$\text{Pt}_9(\text{CO})_9 + \text{Pt}^0(\text{CO})$	8	2.3	183	199	2	2

^a Elongation with respect to the bond length in the isolated in gas phase CO molecule 114.2 pm.

^b Average values for Pt-surface O contacts smaller than 230 pm and the number of contacts.

Table 2. Relative energies (ΔE , kJ/mol) for the transfer of $\text{Pt}(\text{CO})_X$ ($X = 0 - 2$) species from $\text{Pt}_8(\text{CO})_m/\text{Ce}_{12}\text{O}_{24}$ ($m = 0, 7$ or 12) on $\text{Ce}_{21}\text{O}_{42}$ nanoparticle with respect to the initial structures, *e*, *f*, and *g*. Selected distances in the $\text{Pt}(\text{CO})_X$ species (in pm); number of Ce^{3+} cations, N; number of unpaired electrons (Ns) for the systems are also shown.

Structure	Short Description	ΔE	$\Delta d(\text{C-O})^a$	$d(\text{Pt-C})$	$d(\text{Pt-O})$	N	Ns
$\text{Pt}_8/\text{Ce}_{21}\text{O}_{42}$							
<i>e</i>	Pt_8	0			$\langle 205 \rangle^b/5$	2	2
<i>e-Pt-1</i>	$\text{Pt}_7 + \text{Pt}^{2+}$	-189			205;205;205;205	4	2
<i>e-Pt-2</i>	$\text{Pt}_7 + \text{Pt}^0$	86			199;207	2	2
$\text{Pt}_8(\text{CO})_7/\text{Ce}_{21}\text{O}_{42}$							
<i>f</i>	$\text{Pt}_8(\text{CO})_7$	0			$\langle 207 \rangle^b/3$	0	0
<i>f-Pt(CO)₂</i>	$\text{Pt}_7(\text{CO})_5 + \text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$	17	1.0;1.0	189;189	201;201	3	2
<i>f-Pt(CO)</i>	$\text{Pt}_7(\text{CO})_6 + \text{Pt}^0(\text{CO})$	22	2.5	182	201	0	0
$\text{Pt}_8(\text{CO})_{12}/\text{Ce}_{21}\text{O}_{42}$							
<i>g</i>	$\text{Pt}_8(\text{CO})_{12}$	0			$\langle 224 \rangle^b/3$	0	0
<i>g-Pt(CO)₂-1</i>	$\text{Pt}_7(\text{CO})_{10} + \text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$	-75	1.0;1.0	189;189	201;201	4	2
<i>g-Pt(CO)₂-2</i>	$\text{Pt}_7(\text{CO})_{10} + \text{Pt}^{2+}(\text{CO})_2$	-18	0.9;1.0	189;189	200;201	4	2
<i>g-Pt(CO)</i>	$\text{Pt}_7(\text{CO})_{11} + \text{Pt}^0(\text{CO})$	-35	2.6	182	201	0	0

^a Elongation with respect to the bond length in the isolated in gas phase CO molecule 114.2 pm.

^b Average values for Pt-surface O contacts smaller than 230 pm and the number of contacts.

Table 3. Relative energies (ΔE , kJ/mol) for the transfer of $\text{Pt}(\text{CO})_X$ ($X = 0 - 2$) species from $\text{Pt}_{10}(\text{CO})_m$ ($m = 0$ or 9) clusters on $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3(001)$ support with respect to the initial structures h and i . Selected distances in the $\text{Pt}(\text{CO})_X$ species (in pm); number of Ce^{3+} cations, N ; number of unpaired electrons (N_s) for the systems are also shown.

Structure	Short Description	ΔE	$\Delta d(\text{C-O})^a$	$d(\text{Pt-C})$	$d(\text{Pt-O})$	N_s
$\text{Pt}_{10}/\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3(001)$						
h	Pt_{10}	0			$\langle 219 \rangle^{b/3}$	0
$h\text{-Pt}$	$\text{Pt}_9 + \text{Pt}^0$	70			202;205	0
$\text{Pt}_{10}(\text{CO})_9/\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3(001)$						
i	$\text{Pt}_{10}(\text{CO})_9$	0			209, 1 ^c	0
$i\text{-Pt}(\text{CO})_2$	$\text{Pt}_9(\text{CO})_7 + \text{Pt}(\text{CO})_2$	178		Pt(CO) ₂ unit desorbs ^d		2
$i\text{-Pt}(\text{CO})$	$\text{Pt}_9(\text{CO})_8 + \text{Pt}^0(\text{CO})$	57	2.3	181	206	0

^a Elongation with respect to the bond length in the isolated in gas phase CO molecule 114.2 pm.

^b Average value for Pt-surface O contacts smaller than 230 pm and their number.

^c Since there is only one Pt-O contact is referred the exact value.

^d The distance between the Pt from Pt(CO)₂ unit and the nearest surface O is 247 pm.

Table 4. Energetic difference between the products and the reactants (E_{P-R} , in kJ/mol) for the selected reactions per Pt atom.

Reaction	E_{P-R}
CeO₂(111)	
Pt ₁₀ /CeO ₂ +9×CeO ₂ → 10×Pt ⁰ /CeO ₂	94
Pt ₁₀ (CO) ₁₀ /CeO ₂ +9×CeO ₂ → 10×Pt ⁰ (CO)/CeO ₂	2
Pt ₁₀ (CO) ₉ /CeO ₂ +9×CeO ₂ → 4×Pt ²⁺ (CO) ₂ /CeO ₂ +5×Pt ⁰ /CeO ₂ +Pt ⁰ (CO)/CeO ₂	106
Pt ₁₀ (CO) ₁₀ /CeO ₂ +9×CeO ₂ → 5×Pt ²⁺ (CO) ₂ /CeO ₂ +5×Pt ⁰ /CeO ₂	108
Ce₂₁O₄₂ nanoparticle	
Pt ₈ /Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂ +7× Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂ → 8×Pt ²⁺ / Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂	-137
Pt ₈ /Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂ +7× Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂ → 8×Pt ⁰ / Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂	59
Pt ₈ (CO) ₇ / Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂ +7× Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂ → 7×Pt ⁰ (CO)/ Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂ +Pt ²⁺ / Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂	-18
Pt ₈ (CO) ₇ / Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂ +7× Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂ → 7×Pt ⁰ (CO)/ Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂ +Pt ⁰ / Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂	6
Pt ₈ (CO) ₁₂ / Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂ +7× Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂ → 6×Pt ²⁺ (CO) ₂ / Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂ +2×Pt ²⁺ / Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂	-51
Pt ₈ (CO) ₁₂ / Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂ +7× Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂ → 6×Pt ²⁺ (CO) ₂ / Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂ +2×Pt ⁰ / Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂	-2
Pt ₈ (CO) ₁₂ / Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂ +7× Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂ → 4×Pt ²⁺ (CO) ₂ / Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂ +4×Pt ⁰ (CO)/ Ce ₂₁ O ₄₂	-33
γ-Al₂O₃(001)	
Pt ₁₀ /Al ₂ O ₃ +9×Al ₂ O ₃ → 10×Pt ⁰ /Al ₂ O ₃	47
Pt ₁₀ (CO) ₉ /Al ₂ O ₃ +9×Al ₂ O ₃ → 9×Pt ⁰ (CO)/Al ₂ O ₃ +Pt ⁰ /Al ₂ O ₃	39

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